

D8.5

The FAIRness of EISCAT_3D

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Deliverable abstract

This report presents the implementation of the FAIR principles by EISCAT_3D.

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D8.5 – The FAIRness of EISCAT_3D

1 Introduction

The ENVRI-FAIR project’s objective is to implement “FAIRness” for data produced in the European Research Infrastructures (RIs) organized in the Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) community, in order to make them ready for connecting to the European Open Science Cloud¹ (EOSC). In this context, “FAIR”² is an acronym comprising the aspects of “Findable”, “Accessible”, “Interoperable”, and “Reusable” as specified by the FORCE11 community³.

ENVRI-FAIR WP8 organises and conducts this implementation work for the community of ENVRI RIs in the atmospheric subdomain, comprised of the RIs ACTRIS⁴, EISCAT⁵, IAGOS⁶, ICOS⁷ (atmosphere), and SIOS⁸ (atmosphere).

The Deliverable 8.3 Atmospheric subdomain implementation plan⁹, describing the implementation plan of FAIRness for the atmospheric sub-domain, was ready in March 2020. Later, a revised version was produced, taking the implementation of the ENVRI-hub into account. This second version¹⁰ was finalised in September 2021 and is the most recent implementation plan for WP8.

The present deliverable provides the “The FAIRness of EISCAT_3D” and refers to the status of the implementation in relation to the updated second version of the implementation plan from September 2021.

Furthermore, a FAIRness assessment is performed in the first part of 2023 to monitor the complete progress over the project period using FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs). This is ready in April 2023 and will be reported in the Deliverable “D8.13 Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment report” due in May 2023.

2 Background and the starting point for EISCAT_3D

The EISCAT_3D radar system is a major upgrade of the capabilities of EISCAT Scientific Association. At the time when the ENVRI-FAIR project was conceived, the first EISCAT_3D data were expected to be available to the user community towards the end of 2021. However, significant delays in the construction of the EISCAT_3D system due to factors such as the CoViD-19 pandemic and the global shortage of semi-conductor components has had the effect that the EISCAT_3D system is still under construction. Hence, there have been no EISCAT_3D data available at any point during the ENVRI-FAIR project. For that reason, a significant part of the work in the ENVRI-FAIR project has been focused on the status of the data from the present EISCAT systems. EISCAT Scientific Association has been operating incoherent scatter radar systems since 1981 and has therefore collected large amounts of historic data. The ENVRI-FAIR project has still been very valuable for the planning of the structures of future EISCAT_3D metadata and data.

The general work for EISCAT within the ENVRI-FAIR project followed the planned workflow for all five participating Research Infrastructures in the atmospheric sub-domain. That means going through the following steps: analysis of the starting level of FAIRness of the data and the services, preparation of a detailed implementation plan targeting the found gaps, realisation of this plan, and performing a new assessment of the FAIRness of EISCAT at the end of the ENVRI-FAIR project.

¹ European Open Science Cloud: <https://www.eosc-portal.eu>

² FAIR: <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

³ FORCE 11 community: <https://www.force11.org/about>

⁴ ACTRIS: <https://www.actris.eu>

⁵ EISCAT: <https://www.eiscat.se>

⁶ IAGOS: <https://www.iagos.org>

⁷ ICOS: <https://www.icos-ri.eu>

⁸ SIOS: <https://sios-svalbard.org>

⁹ D8.3 Atmospheric subdomain implementation plan: <https://envri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D8.3.pdf>

¹⁰ Second version of the implementation plan: <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/6436>

2.1 Gap analysis

There are two different fundamental types of archived EISCAT data: low-level data (EISCAT data levels 1 and 2), consisting of receiver voltage levels and spectral data, and high-level data (EISCAT data level 3), consisting of altitude profiles of the physical parameters of the ionosphere such as electron density, electron and ion temperatures, and plasma flows. These two data types are handled differently, with different embargo rules and data access systems.

At an early point in the ENVRI-FAIR project, the RIs in the ENVRI atmospheric subdomain conducted a comprehensive analysis of the FAIRness of their data centres, data curation and data management. The conclusions from this initial FAIRness gap analysis of EISCAT data were that:

- no persistent identifiers were used for EISCAT data (Findability)
- the EISCAT data had a weak metadata registry, which was not following any of the established standards (Findability)
- there were no standardised solutions in general for accessing the EISCAT data levels 1 and 2 (Accessibility)
- the system used to access EISCAT level 3 data (Madrigal) was not particularly well known outside of the international geospace community (Accessibility)
- work was needed on the authentication and authorisation to cover the different foreseeable use cases following the EISCAT embargo rules (Accessibility)
- the only available standardised metadata used was the timing of the experiment (Interoperability)
- work had started, but had not been concluded, to ensure inclusion of metadata and enabling interoperability standards (Interoperability)
- gaps existed in the standardisation in areas regarding how the data were produced, processed, and validated (Reusability)
- work had started, but had not been concluded, to ensure inclusion of metadata, enabling provenance attributes (Reusability)

From this analysis the priorities were made to trying to work towards an implementation following standards that are adopted by the community. It was also noted that since EISCAT Scientific Association owns all data that are obtained through its facilities, the responsibility for the FAIRness implementation lies only on one part which simplifies the organisation of the work. The existing EISCAT data policy was, and still is, an agreement signed by all EISCAT member countries, and its general aim is aligned with striving to have a large degree of FAIRness for the data produced by the EISCAT facilities. With the formal data policies in place and a full control of the data management, there would be no fundamental formal barriers to implement a FAIR data management system to handle the expected large volumes of EISCAT_3D data produced when the new radar system is ready and operational.

A more formalised approach of assessing the degree of FAIRness than could be done through this initial gap analysis, was introduced through the concept of FIPs (FAIR Implementation Profiles) that was proposed by the GO-FAIR project . These were adopted by the ENVRI-FAIR project, and yearly assessments using FIPs were performed under the lead of ENVRI-FAIR Work Package 5. Based on the original gap analysis and the first FIP assessment, a detailed implementation plan was developed for EISCAT.

2.2 The FAIR implementation plan for EISCAT

As stated before, the FAIR implementation plan for EISCAT was developed as part of the implementation plan for the atmospheric subdomain (Deliverable 8.3: Atmospheric subdomain implementation plan). This original plan consisted of the following aspects of work:

- PID implementation:
 - Introduce metadata specification using the exposed DataCite¹¹ metadata fields, including assigning a DOI for each Data Collection and PIDs for the Data Sets therein.
 - Secure provenance documentation by referencing data sets by unique IDs of the underlying data and PIDs of the processes operating on it (both software and hardware PIDs).
- Machine-to-machine interface:
 - Introduce harvestable metadata in formats including DataCite. Migrate the present online EISCAT archive of analysed data (Madrigal¹²) to a version with HDF5-based archival. Add an OAI-PMH server for harvesting metadata.
 - Low-level data should not be copied outside the EISCAT e-infrastructures without consent. Preparations should be made so that future EISCAT_3D users can use DIRAC¹³ to search and stage data, submit analysis jobs and retrieve the results. This also means adding high-level API scripts (python, Matlab, IDL) to the DIRAC portal for EISCAT_3D data.
 - Introduce usage of notebooks for users to upload their own analysis software.
- Links to WIS and GEOSS:
 - Introduce an ontology based on the ESPAS ontology¹⁴, since the present GEOSS fields are not sufficient for EISCAT data.
- Authentication schemes:
 - Prepare authentication through EGI Check-in¹⁵ for authentication. EGI Check-in brokers a selection of identity providers (IdPs), like EDUgain, B2access, ORCID, and other social identities including QQ and WeChat. Also introduce additional local login for users outside of the general IdP services, and as a second level authentication for expert users.
 - Introduce authorisation through a local ldap server, using as much as possible automatic selection procedures from the IdP provisions.
- Endpoint towards ENVRI-hub:
 - Utilise the Madrigal python APIs in the ENVRI-hub services.
 - Reformat the internal databases and add metadata sets to harmonise with ENVRI-hub.
- GUI recommendations:
 - Develop structurally new portals to handle the increased complexity of operations and the substantially larger data volumes the EISCAT portals needs to handle when EISCAT_3D is in operation.
 - Implement additions to the current EISCAT portals to allow for the FAIR requirements, and to enable easier transitions to the new portals.
- Provenance:
 - Introduce machine ingestible documentation of the stages the EISCAT data goes through from collection to storage, including the hardware status.

An initial set of internal milestones, with expected finalisation dates, were also prepared for tracking the progress of this work:

- June 2020: DataCite metadata attributes defined for level 3 data.
- June 2020: EGI Checkin implemented for authentication on EISCAT portal for operations.
- June 2020: Upgrade to Madrigal 3.0 with python3 APIs.
- May 2021: Upgrade to the Madrigal vs 3 database for the high-level data.

¹¹ DataCite: <https://datacite.org>

¹² Madrigal: <https://madrigal.eiscat.se/madrigal>

¹³ DIRAC: <https://dirac.egi.eu/DIRAC>

¹⁴ ESPAS ontology: <http://ontology.espas-fp7.eu/vocabs>

¹⁵ EGI Check-In: <https://www.egi.eu/service/check-in>

- September 2021: New data format for basic EISCAT level 3 data (HDF5, metadata with proper description of parameters, provenance metadata, DataCite metadata).
- October 2021: ESPAS ontology entered into datasets.
- October 2021: Define an atmospheric parameter set for EISCAT_3D suitable for WIS and GEOSS.
- October 2021: EGI Checkin implemented for authentication on EISCAT portal for data access purposes.
- October 2021: EGI Checkin implemented for authentication on EISCAT portal for processing purposes.
- October 2021: The hdf5 format of EISCAT data level 3 implemented with a more complete set of provenance links.
- October 2021: EISCAT data levels 1 and 2 converted to hdf5 file format, with provenance information.
- November 2021: Determine granularity levels of Data Collections for DOIs.
- November 2021: DataCite metadata attributes defined for EISCAT data levels 1 and 2.
- December 2021: Links with WIS established for the existing atmospheric data sets.
- December 2021: Proper AAI for embargoed data with EGI-Checkin and group management.
- December 2021: Jupyter notebooks introduced for user access to data.
- January 2022: Implementation of DOIs for all data products based on Data Collections in primary repositories.
- January 2022: Metadata ingestion into B2FIND.
- January 2022: OAI-PMH interfaced to the DIRAC file catalogue.
- May 2022: Provenance PIDs created following an agreed schema.
- June 2022: Machinery implemented to publish PIDs for data used in publications.
- June 2022: Madrigal APIs harmonised with ENVRI services.
- December 2022: APIs implemented for all levels of data.
- December 2022: Launching EISCAT_3D operations portal.
- December 2022: Launching EISCAT_3D data management system based on DIRAC.

This initial implementation plan was later updated throughout the project to reflect on changes in the target, in particular due to the delayed implementation of the EISCAT_3D system.

3 Progress on FAIRness for EISCAT

The progress of the implementation of FAIRness for EISCAT is easiest illustrated in the form of Table 1 on next page, where the tasks in the implementation plan are listed including markers displaying the status of the tasks at the time of the three different project Milestones (MS40 – June 2020, MS42 – October 2021, MS44 – September 2022).

From Table 1 it is clear that the FAIRness status of EISCAT is not exactly where it was planned to be at the end point of the ENVRI-FAIR project, but it is also clear that good progress has been made in most of the areas. As stated before, the main reason behind the divergences from the original plan has been the delays in the implementation of the EISCAT_3D system which was required for some of the planned development work.

Table 1: Summary of implementation of FAIRness for EISCAT_3D

Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month	Progress		
		MS40	MS42	MS44
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
EISCAT: determine DOI granularity	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: product DOIs implemented	1st QTR 22			
EISCAT: PID publication	2nd QTR 22			
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
EISCAT: DataCite metadata defined (Level 3)	2nd QTR 20			
EISCAT: DataCite metadata defined (Level 1&2)	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: metadata ingested in B2FIND	1st QTR 22			
EISCAT: OAI-PMH interface available	1st QTR 22			
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
EISCAT: ontology updated	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: set up WIS compatible metadata	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: link to WIS established	4th QTR 21			
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
EISCAT: authentication for operations	2nd QTR 21			
EISCAT: authentication for data	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: authentication for processing	4th QTR 21			
1.5 Service endpoint to ENVRI-hub				
EISCAT: Update to Madrigal 3	1st QTR 21			
EISCAT: Harmonise Madrigal APIs with ENVRI	2nd QTR 22			
EISCAT: Implement APIs for all data levels	4th QTR 22			
1.6 GUI recommendations				
EISCAT: database upgrade	2nd QTR 21			
EISCAT: new data format	3rd QTR 21			
EISCAT: AAI implemented	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: new portal implemented	3rd QTR 22			
1.7 Document provenance				
EISCAT: new data format, more provenance	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: use PIDs	1st QTR 22			
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	3rd QTR 22			
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 21			
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	1st QTR 21			
2.4 Semantic search	1st QTR 21			
2.5 Graphical user interfaces	3rd QTR 22			

	Completed
	In progress
	Not started, according to plan
	Delay

4 Remaining tasks

Some of the tasks have changed direction during the ENVRI-FAIR project, partly reflecting the EISCAT_3D delays but also due to the PITHIA-NRF project¹⁶. That is an EU Horizon 2020 project starting in 2021 aiming at building a European distributed network that integrates observing facilities, data processing tools and prediction models dedicated to ionosphere, thermosphere and plasmasphere research.

In progress:

- Registration of EISCAT data and instruments in the PITHIA e-science centre. The EISCAT radar data registration is ready, and the system itself is soon available for access by the public. This process is streamlining the process for EISCAT in the ENVRI-FAIR context.
- Registration of EISCAT services in the ENVRI Catalogue of services, which is an ongoing effort. Some assistance with the dataset descriptions (RDF/Turtle) will be required to finalise this, and it will be done as soon as possible.
- The plans are still to set up an OAI-PMH endpoint that can serve EISCAT's DataCite metadata to B2FIND. This work will be done during 2023.

Need revision of plans:

- The introduction of licences for the use of EISCAT data, metadata and documentation requires a high-level decision from the EISCAT Council.
- The terms of service and usage have to be updated to follow modern standard requirements.
- The choice of which PID system to use (handle versus DOI). The access to DOI will have to be possible through PITHIA-NRF, EOSC and/or some other manner.

Not relevant anymore:

- Some considerations in the plan were based on the assumption that the DIRAC system would be used for access to data and other resources. This is no longer part of the plans for EISCAT.

5 Main achievements and improvement of FAIRness for EISCAT_3D

EISCAT has reached a number of achievements and made improvements of its FAIRness during the ENVRI-FAIR project.

A metadata specification has been implemented using exposed DataCite metadata fields. This includes assigning a DOI for each data collection and PIDs for the data sets therein.

In order to secure proper provenance documentation, the EISCAT data sets are now referenced by unique IDs of the underlying data (allowing database queries) and PIDs of the processes operating on it, including both software PIDs and hardware PIDs. This approach is planned to be used for all levels of data, from the lowest voltages samples to the final data products and the implementation has started.

EISCAT has started implementing plans to make the metadata harvestable in various formats, including DataCite, and possibly other standards. The existing EISCAT archive of analysed data, Madrigal, has been migrated to a new version, Madrigal 3, with HDF5-based archival. An OAI-PMH server for harvesting metadata is planned to be added to Madrigal 3 and B2FIND will harvest its metadata. The Madrigal database has API script examples available for several high-level languages such as Python, Matlab and IDL.

Work at EISCAT has been directed towards using the ESPAS ontology as the GEOSS fields have been found not to be sufficient.

¹⁶ PITHIA-NRF: <https://pithia-nrf.eu>

EISCAT has implemented a system based on EGIcheckin for authentication. In addition, a local login for will be implemented for users outside of the general Ipd services, and for a second level authentication for administrative level users.

For the authorisation, a local ldap server will be set up using as much as possible automatic selection procedures from the Ipd provisions. For some users, it is necessary to add specific rules to adhere to the EISCAT data embargo rules.

EISCAT will utilise the Madrigal pythonAPIs in the ENVRI-hub services (Task 8.5 in ENVRI-FAIR). EISCAT has reformatted its internal databases while adding metadata sets to harmonise with ENVRI-Hub.

EISCAT has for a long time been running web-based portals for operation, and for accessing low-level and high-level data. They have been developed following a structure suitable for the EISCAT systems currently in operation. With the construction of EISCAT_3D, the increased complexity of operations and the substantially larger data volumes, structurally new portals are about to be developed. To approach the FAIR requirements, some additions to the current portals need to be implemented, mainly to enable an easier transition to the newer systems. However, this work has been delayed due to the delays in the implementation of the EISCAT_3D system.

The EISCAT data go through a number of stages of different nature. Some are relatively simple, like filtering, and some are more complicated, such as the derivation of physical parameters. Additionally, the hardware sometimes goes through various levels of development. The majority of these issues are well documented, but most of them are not machine ingestible. During this project, some effort has been spent on making some of them at least restful linkable in the metadata.

5.1 What can we do now which we could not before the advancing of the FAIRness?

- EISCAT now has a standardised and secure system for authentication and authorisation for services and access to data. This has made it possible to use Jupyter notebooks for data access and verification.
- Metadata is now included according to DataCite by default.
- HDF5-based data archives have been developed and are now in use.
- Vocabularies are standardised, as well as the data provenance.
- EISCAT personnel is now familiarised with RDF/Turtle/triplestores etc.
- EISCAT data service is ready to be included into ENVRI hub.

5.2 What would we like to do and achieve within the next 5 years?

- We would really like to have the EISCAT_3D system ready, producing data of high quality. Hence, we would like to deploy a data archive for EISCAT_3D.
- We also would like to enable searches for patterns of data (for instance looking for signatures of specific ionospheric conditions).
- The EISCAT datasets should be complete, and the metadata should be harvestable in selectable formats.
- We should have PIDs available where it is relevant (for citable datasets, notebooks, workflows, etc)
- Finally, we want to ensure that the (extended) EISCAT community will be familiar with all of the above.